

WP2 Methodology Note

A key-informant interview study with Bulgarian agri-food branch organisations on NGT (CRISPR-edited) products

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1. Purpose and design

The study is a semi-structured key-informant interview study of senior representatives (presidents, secretary generals, designated public-relations officers) of Bulgarian agri-food branch organisations. The unit of analysis is the publicly articulable position of the organisation, accessed through senior representatives, in the tradition of the German-language ExpertInneninterview.

2. Sampling

Sampling is purposive and stratified by sub-sector, with snowball expansion. The sampling frame is constructed from four publicly verifiable sources and targeted key-informant referrals from senior experts with operational experience in the Bulgarian agri-food sector. Inclusion criteria are senior representative status, capacity to speak on the policy positions of the organisation, and consent to audio recording. The target sample is eleven to twelve interviewees, with a floor of ten and a ceiling of fourteen if the saturation criterion has not been met by the twelfth interview.

3. Saturation criterion

The criterion distinguishes between code saturation, defined as the point at which no substantively new first-level codes emerge, and meaning saturation, defined as full elaboration of identified themes. Following empirical benchmarks for relatively homogeneous expert populations, code saturation is expected to emerge around the ninth interview. Operationally, saturation is claimed only when two consecutive interviews yield no new first-level codes and no substantive new dimensions of existing codes. The target sample of eleven to twelve interviews is calibrated to allow saturation to emerge organically, to provide at least two confirmation interviews beyond the point of first apparent saturation, and to ensure coverage of all stratification sub-sectors. If saturation is not demonstrated by the twelfth interview, recruitment continues up to the fifteenth interview.

4. Analytic strategy

The analytic strategy is framework analysis. Coding proceeds in five stages: familiarisation with full transcripts; construction of an initial coding framework deductively; indexing of transcripts against the framework; inductive emergence of additional themes; and charting, mapping and interpretation. An independent second coder codes a random subset of the transcripts; inter-rater agreement is assessed and discrepancies resolved through discussion, with the coding framework refined where the discussion reveals coding-schema ambiguity rather than judgement difference.

5. Ethics and data protection

Informed consent is obtained in writing prior to each interview using the deposited Consent Form template (Bulgarian). The expected interview duration is 45 to 60 minutes, consistent with the duration approved by the ethics committees. Pseudonymisation occurs at transcription. Storage is on the secured Agroscope servers, in line with the Data Management Plan (DMP) submitted to the Swiss National Science Foundation under project IZSF-0_235780. Data processing complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; Regulation (EU) 2016/679) and the Bulgarian Personal Data Protection Act. The hosting institution and data controller is Agroscope (Federal Research Institute for Agriculture). The

procedural instruments of the study contain no personal data within the meaning of GDPR Art. 4(1) or the Bulgarian Personal Data Protection Act, and are pre-registered on a repository aligned with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), such as Zenodo, under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 (CC BY 4.0) licence prior to the first interview. Ethics approval has been obtained from two independent Bulgarian ethics committees: (i) the Ethics Committee of Sofia University Sv. Kliment Ohridski in April 2026 (ref. 93-K-72/17.04.2026; chair Prof. Dr Romyana Marinova-Hristidi); and (ii) the Ethics Committee of the Bulgarian Sociological Association in May 2026 (session of 15.05.2026; chair Prof. Dr Tatyana Kotseva).

6. Deposit contents and citation

The deposit contains the following files: this Methodology Note, the Interview Guide, the Informed Consent Form template (Bulgarian, for the semi-structured branch-organisation interviews), and the Recruitment Protocol. The deposit is licensed CC BY 4.0. Suggested citation: Mihaylova, I. (2026). Preregistration — Project SciEx IZSF-0_235780 Working Package WP2: Interview instrument and methodology: A key-informant interview study with Bulgarian agri-food branch organisations on NGT (CRISPR-edited) products. Zenodo. Digital Object Identifier (DOI) to be assigned at deposit.